

THE ROLE OF READING SKILLS IN LEARNING A FOREIGN

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Abstract: As reading is one of the most important means of obtaining information and it has a significant place in the life of an educated person, this article deals with the role of reading skill in learning a foreign language.

Key words: Reading skill, skimming, scanning, intensive, extensive.

Аннотация: Поскольку чтение является одним из важнейших средств получения информации и занимает значительное место в жизни образованного человека, в данной статье рассматривается роль навыка чтения в изучении иностранного языка.

Ключевые слова: Навык чтения, беглый просмотр, сканирование, интенсивный, экстенсивный.

English is one of the most widely spoken languages in almost all countries of the world. The overgrowing need for fluency in English throughout the world has led linguists and teachers to prioritize the search for more effective ways of teaching language skills, one of which is reading. In this article, it considers the importance of reading in the study and teaching of English or any other foreign language, presents approaches to teaching reading that can be used in reading and parsing any text, introduces various strategies in teaching reading, and describes common ways of teaching reading to students in the classroom. Reading skills lead a person to interact and gain meaning from written language⁵. Reading is a means of language acquisition, communication and of sharing information and ideas. Reading comprehension is an active reading to get information and to create meaning from reading materials by integrating what to be end into what has already known. So that students understand the material. Reading is a receptive skill besides listening. It becomes a fundamental factor for students to produce writing.

Reading is one of the most important skills in language learning. Reading is one of English skill that is very important that should be taught and delivered well.

⁵ Yugay, E. V. (2021). Digital culture and its influence on value aspects of human being. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. Soi: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-12-104-29> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/IAS.2021.12.104.29>

Reading comprehension skills can be acquired easily through positive communication between the educator and the learner. Reading needs to be approached as a disciplinary practice linked to knowledge-build rather than as a discrete skill.

Reading is important for every people. In foreign language learning, reading is likewise a skill that teacher simply expects learners to acquire reading arguably become the most essential skill for success in all educational context, remains a skill of paramount importance as we create assessment of general language ability. Reading instruction often aims to develop students’ decoding skills and knowledge of syntax or vocabulary for literal comprehension. Reading is closely connected with the pronunciation of human skills, which help to form the fugitive reading technique. Reading plays a major role in the process of learning a foreign language. Reading is the purpose and means of learning a foreign language. The goal of reading instruction is to give students the ability to read a foreign language, which is one of the practical purposes of studying of this discipline. When considering different types of reading skills, a short list of four strategies, or reading styles, may come to mind. These are:

1. Skimming;
2. Scanning;
3. Intensive;
4. Extensive.

Activity 1. There is the given text. This activity requires from pupils read carefully this text, after that they should find an appropriate title.

Today history was made. The new national music conservatoire in Tashkent opened its doors to the public. At last we have a building which honors our great musicians. Uzbekistan has long cultural roots. Many famous people have contributed to the great wealth that we have today. In the field of music some of the best known are Mamurjon Uzokov, Juraxon Sulstonov, Tukhtasin Jalilov, Ganijon Toshmatov, Yunus Rajabi, Dilorom Omonullaeva, Alisher Ikromov and Abduhoshim Ismoilov.

Uzbekistan values its cultural traditions and supports and develops the next generation who will add to them. For this purpose two festivals called “Umid Yulduzlari” have been held recently, one in December 2001 and another in February 2002. The goal of the festivals is to find and support young soloists and musicians. But that is not the only purpose. Many school pupils were also invited to attend the festivals to help them to develop a love for music so that it become part of their lives too. The festivals, together with the opening of the new Music Conservatoire in Tashkent, are major steps the development of music in Uzbekistan.

5. Here are following headings:
6. A). Music festivals;
7. B). Tashkent conservatoire;
8. C). Classical music and dance;

9. D). My favourite music.

In conclusion, taking everything into account, reading helps the formation of reading comprehension. Finally, it will be noticed that without reading skills, language learning is impossible. This is because there is no communication where there is no human interaction. Also, reading is main not only in language learning but also for learning other spheres⁶. But even nowadays with all the technological developments in the field of education, learners have problems with reading. Though these activities students improve their reading skills and they learn how to use scanning and skimming while-reading task. These are some kind of offers to deal with the obstacles in reading as well as to develop the reading skills of students.

Bibliography:

1. Антрушина, Г.Б. Лексикология английского языка/ Г.Б. Антрушина. - М.: Дрофа, 2001.-288с.
2. Ариян, М.А. Пути совершенствования профессиональной компетенции учителя иностранного языка / М.А. Ариян // Иностранные языки в школе.-2003.-№1-С.86-90.
3. Ибрагимова, З.Н. The role of reading in the process of foreign language teaching.
4. <https://moluch.ru/conf/phil/archive/235/12042/>
5. Югай Е. Digital culture and society: problems of their relationship in the conditions of globalization //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 7/S. – С. 58-67.
6. <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss7/S-pp58-67>
7. Yugay, E. V. (2021). Digital culture and its influence on value aspects of human being. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. SoI: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-12-104-29> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.12.104.29>

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